

ISic0119

I.Sicily inscription 0119

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. L(ucio) Acilio
2. Advento
3. Helias pio
4. coiugiconiugi

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

Translation (en)

Helias (made this) for her dutiful husband Lucius Acilius Adventus.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284768

EDR 033608; 111000

EDCS 22100070

PHI 313702

Bibliography

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